

NEW MULTIFUNCTIONAL HYBRID POLYMER COMPOSITES REINFORCED BY CARBON AND STEEL FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

The challenges of society and politics for next generation aircraft are highly ambitious. On top of major improvements in the field of aerodynamic and propulsion technology, significant advancements of the airframe structure are required. Efforts must focus on manufacturing efficiency as well as on breakthrough solutions for damage tolerance and function integration. Compared to aluminum alloys, contemporary CFRP solutions for airframe structures offer poor electrical conductivity. Additional metal elements are necessary to fulfill important electrical functions (e.g., lightning strike protection, electromagnetical shielding, electrical bonding and grounding), compromising CFRP's lightweight potential. Moreover, CFRP shows brittle failure behavior, limiting the structural integrity in crash load cases. The limited damage tolerance against probable impact events also leads to a minimum wall thickness criterion. Against this background, a new hybrid composite material consisting of reinforcing carbon and metal fibers embedded in an epoxy matrix is investigated. Basic idea of this material concept is to merge electrical and load-bearing functions by incorporated highly conductive and ductile stainless steel fibers. The increased density of the composite is overcompensated by eliminating the need for additional electrical system installation items and the enhanced damage tolerance, resulting in a reduced minimum wall thickness. The present study focus on optimizing the electrical and mechanical properties of the composite. Material tests are conducted on unidirectional coupons with different steel fiber volume fractions to demonstrate the potential of this novel hybrid composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Pushed by the need for further mass reduction and structural performance improvements, artificial composites have been increasingly used by airframe manufacturers over the last years. Today, CFRP is the primary choice for aircraft load carrying structures. Contemporary aircrafts such as Boeing's B787 or Airbus' A350 consist of more than 50 weight percentage of this composite [1, 4].

In order to contribute to further mass reduction of next generation airframes and the subsequent secondary effects, efforts must focus on affordable design and material improvements. Former research attempts concentrated on modifying the polymer matrix systems. By introduction of conductive particles like carbon nano tubes, the specific conductance of CFRP could be enhanced [9]. However, a sufficient level of conductivity which would guarantee electrical function integration for the modified CFRP similar to that of aluminum alloys and GLARE[®] airframe structures could not be demonstrated. The impact damage tolerance of thin-walled CFRP structures has gradually been improved by the addition of polymer toughening agents. Thermoplastic polymers and rubber particles were introduced in epoxy resin systems in different ways for prepregs, enabling substantial improvements of fracture toughness and residual strength. However, even for CFRP airframe

structures fabricated with the latest generation of toughened prepreg systems, damage tolerance against probable impact events can be the limiting design driver.

2 METAL CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES

Unlike former research attempts dealing with modified polymer matrix systems, the improvement of important composite properties as well as the integration of electrical functions by means of reinforcing metal fiber incorporation is a promising new approach. Research results in [2, 7, 8, 11] show significant improvements in terms of energy absorption, fail safe behavior and structural integrity, when classical composites were reinforced by steel. The metal fibers may be distributed homogenously in the composite (homogenized layer approach) or locally concentrated in separate layers (separated layer approach). Basic idea of this material concept is to merge electrical and load-bearing functions in the metal fiber, Figure 1.

CFRP	New material	Metal
+ High stiffness	+ High stiffness	+ High stiffness
+ High strength	+ High strength	+ High strength
+ Very low density	+ Acceptable density	- High density
- Brittle failure	+ Optimized failure	+ Ductile failure
- Poor tensile energy absorption	o Good tensile energy absorption	+ High tensile energy absorption
+ High pressure energy absorption	+ High pressure energy absorption	+ High pressure energy absorption
- Limited crash structure integrity	+ Good crash structure integrity	+ Superior crash structure integrity
- Poor electrical conductivity	+ Sufficient electrical conductivity	+ High electrical conductivity

Figure 1: Benefits of metal and carbon fiber reinforced composite

The increased density of the hybrid composite must be overcompensated by the benefit of eliminating additional electrical system installation items and a reduced minimum wall thickness, exploiting its improved electrical conductivity and damage tolerance. The use of thin metal filaments is also advantageous for design reasons. Different to fiber-metal-laminates such as GLARE[®] or ARALL[®], the fiber based approach enables stress tailored composite design and multiple shaped structures. Furthermore, fully automated manufacturing technologies can be explored by means of processes that are already available for CFRP (e.g., weaving processes for non-crimped fabric manufacturing, automated fiber placement and autoclave technology). However, potential metal fibers have to meet various requirements, in particular superior electrical conductivity, distinctive failure strain, high strength, low density, corrosion resistance, appropriate thermal expansion, availability and low costs, Figure 2.

Aluminum fibers are distinguished by superior weight specific electrical and mechanical properties. However, in contact with carbon fibers, aluminum tends to ineligibile galvanic corrosion. This is of no relevance for stainless steel fibers. Stainless steel fibers are commercially available with a wide range of mechanical properties and appearance. The properties depend not only on the alloy composition and the heat treatment but on the filament diameter as well. Typically, decreasing the diameter leads to a lower ultimate strain to failure. Compared to a standard high tenacity ex-PAN carbon fiber, the electrical conductivity of soft annealed stainless steel fibers (AISI 304) is about 24 times higher. At the same time, the deformation capability can be 16 times higher, while the ultimate tensile strength

(UTS) is five times lower. The stiffness for tensile load of carbon and stainless steel fibers is comparable [10].

	Aluminum	Copper	Steel
Density	+	-	-
Ultimate tensile strength	o	-	+
Failure strain	+	+	+
Thermal expansion	-	+	o
Electr. conductivity	+	+	o
Therm. conductivity	o	+	-
Corrosion resistance	-	+	+
Costs	o	-	+

Figure 2: Comparison of potential metal fiber materials

Due to less alloying elements, unalloyed steel fibers have an even higher specific conductance, but worse mechanical properties. By using nickel or copper cladding, the electrical conductivity of steel fibers can be further enhanced up to a factor of 140 or 390, respectively.

3 MATERIAL PREPARATION

In order to validate the electrical and mechanical properties of carbon and steel fiber reinforced epoxy resin, unidirectional laminates were manufactured by a combined process of tape deposition and filament winding technology. Unidirectional layers of preimpregnated high tenacity carbon fibers were stacked on a flat steel core and wrapped in dry stainless steel fiber bundles. Each bundle consists of seven twisted filaments with a diameter of 60 μm . Both electrical and strain rate dependent mechanical properties of the bundles are known from previous tests, Figure 3.

	Carbon fiber	Stainless steel fiber
Density / g/cm^3	1.77	7.95 ± 0.01
Tensile modulus / GPa	240 ± 3	176 ± 7
Ultimate tensile strength / MPa	$4'806 \pm 125$	897 ± 2
Failure strain / %	$1.85 \pm 0,04$	32.31 ± 2.01
Electr. resistivity / $\Omega\cdot\text{m}$	1.6×10^{-5}	$(6.97 \pm 0,02) \times 10^{-7}$
Filament diameter	5	$60.0 \pm 0,4$
Roving size	12k	7

Figure 3: Properties of applied carbon and stainless steel fibers

Additionally, pure CFRP and SFRP were prepared as reference material. All laminates were cured at 180°C for three hours using autoclave technology and subsequently released from the winding core. By this procedure, six multilayered laminates with different fiber volume fractions and a cured thickness of approximately 1 mm were manufactured, Table 1. Finally, specimens were retrieved from the cured plates by means of water jet cutter technology and prepared for testing.

Laminate	Stacking sequence ^{a)}	Carbon fiber fraction (vol.%) ^{b)}	Steel fiber fraction (vol.%) ^{b)}	Cross section
CFRP	$(0_4^C)_s$	64	0	
SFRP	$(0_7^R/0_3^S)_s$	0	59	
SCFRP 1	$(0_1^S/0_1^C/0_1^S/0_1^C/0_1^S/0_1^C/0_1^S/0_1^C)_s$	52	10	
SCFRP 2	$(0_1^S/0_1^C/0_1^S/0_1^C/0_1^S/0_1^C/0_1^S/0_1^C)_s$	47	18	
SCFRP 3	$(0_3^C/0_1^S)_s$	46	21	
SCFRP 4	$(0_1^S/0_3^C)_s$	46	21	

^{a)} C = Carbon fiber prepreg, S = Stainless steel fiber, R = Resin film

^{b)} Calculated values

Table 1: Architecture and fiber volume fractions of manufactured and analyzed composites

4 ANALYTICAL ESTIMATIONS

The specific conductance measures a material's ability to conduct an electric current. For a conductor with a uniform cross section, the electrical conductivity κ is defined as

$$\kappa = S \cdot \frac{l}{A} \quad (1)$$

where S is the conductance, A the cross-sectional area and l the length of the specimen. The inverse quantity is called the specific electrical resistance ρ . Based on the electrical properties of its components, the electrical conductivity of a perfect unidirectional endless fiber reinforced polymer can be estimated by means of the rule of mixture. Longitudinal to the fiber direction, the composite can be considered as a parallel circuit of several conductors. The overall conductivity is given by

$$S = \sum_i S_i \quad (2)$$

Regarding the volume fraction of its components φ_i , the mean specific conductance along the fiber orientation κ can be calculated considering the volume fractions and the corresponding electrical conductivities κ_i

$$\kappa = \sum_i \kappa_i \cdot \varphi_i \quad (3)$$

This relation for a three-component composite with a constant resin fraction of 40 vol.% is shown in Figure 4, assuming an electrical conductivity of 1.43×10^6 S/m for stainless steel fibers and 6.25×10^4 S/m for high tenacity carbon fibers [10].

Figure 4: Specific electrical resistance and density of a hybrid composite

Following this theoretical approach, a steel/carbon fiber hybrid composite should demonstrate an electrical conductivity of more than 5 times the conductivity of pure CFRP for a steel fiber fraction of 10 vol.% and 8 times for a steel fiber fraction of 20 vol.%. In the meantime, the density rises from 1.59 to 2.20 g/cm³ and 2.82 g/cm³ (for comparison aluminum: 2.71 g/cm³). Regarding an electrical conductivity of 2.36×10^7 S/m for commercially available copper clad low carbon steel fibers, the overall conductivity of the hybrid composite can be increased by a factor of 64 and 127, respectively.

5 MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

5.1 Mechanical properties

Monotonic tensile tests longitudinal to the fiber orientation were performed with a hydraulic testing machine of type Zwick Roell HTM 50/20 in dependence on DIN EN ISO 527-5:2010-01. The rectangular specimens were sized 250 mm × 15 mm and provided with 3 mm thick chamfered aluminum end tabs. The specimens were clamped with a gauge length of 150 mm and loaded with a test speed of 3 mm/s. The deformation was recorded by a high-speed camera Redlake Y4 speed 3 and interpreted by an optical 2D measuring system. The obtained stress-strain curves are summarized in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Tensile stress-strain diagrams of different composite materials

CFRP and the hybrid composites (SCFRP 1 and 2) show a linear elastic behavior with similar stiffness and strains at failure of approximately 1.7%. The mean ultimate tensile strength decreases from 2'463 MPa to 2'298 MPa and 2'078 MPa with an increasing steel fiber fraction. By contrast, pure SFRP shows a pronounced ductile material performance with a yield strength of 349 MPa, a UTS of 509 MPa and an ultimate strain at failure of 14.8%.

Furthermore, flexure tension tests were carried out on a conventional testing machine of type Zwick 1474. For this purpose, rectangular coupons in the form of 125 mm length and 15 mm width flat strips were clamped at their short edges with a remaining span of 50 mm and centrally loaded by a rounded indenter with a cross head speed of 2 mm/min. The supports were chamfered with 5 mm radius. Fibers were orientated in parallel to the long edge of the specimen. Typical force-displacement curves are given in Figure 6. The integrals of the curves yield the absorbed deformation energy.

Figure 6: Force-displacement diagrams for combined tension-bending load

Pure CFRP shows a brittle material performance. Failure occurs abruptly and singularly with a bearable deformation of 3.58 mm. By contrast, the incorporation of stainless steel fibers into CFRP causes to a noticeable post failure behavior. In case of the hybrid composites with homogenously distributed stainless steel fibers, first failure occurs at 3.36 mm (SCFRP 1) and 3.24 mm (SCFRP 2), respectively. Afterwards, the coupons can be further loaded at a reduced level of force. Total failure is reached at an increased deflection of 6.11 mm and 6.33 mm, respectively. An even better material performance can be realized by localizing the metal fibers in the core (SCFRP 3) or top layers (SCFRP 4) of the hybrid laminate. Again, similar to the other composites, first failure occurs at 3.48 mm and 4.00 mm, respectively. However, the maximum deflection can be further enhanced up to 6.96 mm and 10.79 mm, while the force remains on a higher level compared to the homogenized SCFRPs. Pure SFRP bears a deflection of 18.32 mm.

5.2 Electrical properties

Electrical conductivity measurements for the laminate in-plane properties were examined by four wires Ohms measurements on a LabVIEW-based data logging system. For this purpose, direct current (DC) was applied to the short faces of rectangular specimens via copper electrodes with a defined

pressure. Concerning the significant difference in electrical conductivity of carbon fibers and dielectric polymer matrix, the contact between composite sheet and metallic electrode is inherently discontinuous. To reduce the influence of contact resistance the following procedure was applied. The short faces of the specimen were prepared with a grit of 32, cleaned by ethanol and brushed with a silver conductive paste. The surface temperature was monitored during the conductivity experiments by IR-thermography to exclude thermal-induced changes of the electrical conductivity. The experimental setup is given in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Experimental setup for electrical properties: (1) IR-Thermography, (2) specimen fixture with copper electrodes, (3) DC-supply, (4) voltage metering

For a period of 10 seconds a various direct current of 200 mA in maximum was applied to the specimen. The reading was repeated for specimen length of 30 to 250 mm. The voltage was metered for DC stages of 10, 20, 50, 100 and 200 mA. Based on the specific geometry of each and every specimen the specific electrical conductivity was calculated by Ohm's law. The results of the conductivity measurements for the different composite configurations are summarized in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Electrical conductivity of unidirectional CFRP, SFRP and SCFRP

6 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

In case of pure monotonic tensile load, both CFRP and the hybrid composites show brittle material performances with comparable ultimate strains to failure. Despite the incorporation of highly ductile stainless steel fibers, a pronounced post failure behavior could not yet be demonstrated with the analyzed material samples. Due to the homogenous stress state and material deformation, the carbon fibers generate elastic energy on the entire length of the specimen. At the time of their failure, this energy is suddenly released and transferred by the matrix to the ductile steel fibers. However, this energy transfer is limited very locally at the point of failure. By this means, the available ductility of the steel fibers can only be addressed on a small scale, causing a slight macroscopic elongation. Improvements are expected by higher steel fiber fractions (i.e., less elastic energy that must be absorbed by a bigger amount of steel fibers), but would cause higher material densities. This assumption is supported by the test results of pure SFRP, which demonstrate a pronounced plastic deformation. Furthermore, a reduced fiber-resin-adhesion could enable unhindered deformation of the metal fibers over longer distances.

Figure 9: Energy-displacement diagrams for combined tension-bending load

The potential of incorporated steel fibers for an improved fracture and impact behavior of the hybrid composite gets clearer with the flexure tension tests. As in many applications, load is very

locally introduced. High stress peaks occur in the loaded regions, while stress states in the rest of the specimen are significantly lower. In case of the hybrid composites, a certain level of force can be obtained due to the incorporated steel fibers. Related to the very local loading, the carbon fibers store only a small amount of elastic energy. After sudden failure of the carbon fibers, the steel fibers continue to yield without failure and bear further deflections. The enhanced maximum deflection leads to an increase in energy absorption of 25% for SCFRP 1 and 53% for SCFRP 2, in comparison with pure CFRP. Positioning the steel fibers in the top or core layers of the laminate can further enhance the damage tolerance of the composite. In case of SCFRP 3, the stiff and strong carbon fibers in the top layer enable a higher resistance against bending, while the steel fibers in the core layer can plasticize and maximize the structural integrity. The energy absorption can be increased by 145%. In case of SCFRP 4 the steel fibers in the outer plies sustain the bearing cross section until higher deflections. By this means, the energy absorption can be risen by 173%.

The experimental findings of the electrical measurements show a pronounced increase of electrical conductivity as a function of stainless steel fibers volume content. The hybrid composite reinforced with 20 vol.% stainless steel fibers (SCFRP 2) are characterized by the highest electrical conductivity which is about three times higher than conventional CFRP. The observed increased standard deviation of the SCFRP in comparison to CFRP is explainable by the complex contact conditions due to the three different phases of the SCFRP and the copper electrodes. However, the theoretical potential could not yet be verified by these experiments, as the measured conductivities remained below the calculated values derived in chapter 4.

7 CONCLUSION & OUTLOOK

Several advantages of CFRP in comparison to aluminum alloys led to an increasing share of this composite in aviation industry. However, its comparatively poor electrical conductivity and limited damage tolerance require additional systems and elements, compromising today's CFRP lightweight potential. For this reason, efforts must concentrate on modifying CFRP in order to guarantee the necessary electrical functionality for system installation purposes and to improve its damage tolerance.

Unlike former research attempts with modified polymer matrix systems, this study analyzes the potential of a hybrid composite consisting of reinforcing carbon and stainless steel fibers in an epoxy matrix. Compared to state of the art CFRP, significant enhancements of electrical and mechanical key properties could be proved. By incorporation of stainless steel fibers into CFRP, the electrical conductivity can be increased. The deflection in case of bending load and therefore the potential energy absorption can significantly be risen. The results suggest that an allocation of steel fibers in core or top layers is advantageous over a homogenous steel fiber distribution. However, in case of pure tensile load, the deformability of the stainless steel fiber could not yet be exploited to induce a global post failure process. Future steps will address the available deformability of the incorporated steel fibers on more spacious areas of hybrid composites with a limited amount of steel fibers.

In the future, the gained insights have to be transferred to complex, multidirectional composites with (electrical and mechanical) optimized lay-up and complemented by further analysis, e.g., CAI, fatigue, corrosion resistance. Furthermore, the usability of integrated austenitic steel fibers for in-situ health monitoring (based on phase transition and the change of electrical resistivity) and inductive heating for advanced manufacturing processes will be investigated.

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